

Assembly Theory part 1: fundamental concepts and historical development

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Assembly Theory (AT) is a theoretical framework developed to distinguish between abiotic and biotic molecules, particularly in the search for extra-terrestrial life. It posits that life processes uniquely generate complex molecules in large quantities, measured through a mass spectroscopy-inspired metric based on the number of fragments required for hierarchical reconstruction. AT employs an algorithm resembling compression techniques to calculate the minimum assembly steps, proposed as a measure of the selectivity imposed by life processes. However, critics note that mass spectroscopy fragmentation does not correspond to the reverse of molecular synthesis and that AT relies on geometric manipulation rules lacking prebiotic relevance. Direct analysis using spectroscopic data or molecular weights may provide a more accurate and straightforward alternative for predicting biotic origin.

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INTRODUCTION

Assembly Theory (AT) has become perhaps the hottest topic in scientific discussions lately, driven primarily by an unprecedented social and mass media marketing campaign.

Following a comprehensive analysis of Lee Cronin's publications, along with those of his collaborators, as well as their press releases, YouTube videos, and social media posts, Mexican mathematician Zenil observed in an online blog that,

Assembly Theory is a hypothesis that claims to explain selection and evolution and to redefine time, life, and the universe. The authors and some media have gone as far as calling it a Theory of Everything... (Zenil, 2023)

In this three-part series, Part 1 examines the historical context of Assembly Theory (AT), exploring its foundational concepts and less contentious elements. Part 2 assesses the overstated claims surrounding AT, distinguishing those with potential

scientific validity. Part 3 evaluates AT's core premise that complex objects can be constructed in large quantities through a hierarchical assembly process, starting from minimal essential components. Additionally, it critically examines the merits of using the shortest assembly pathway as a metric for chemical complexity. We conclude that AT's concept of "selection" is multifaceted but, if interpreted as a singular force, implies an active, intentional will—akin to a cognizant designer with prior knowledge of the target objects.

AT has become a controversial topic. Therefore, we will quote extensively from the original literature. This will identify any potential misunderstanding on our part, and permit the authors of AT publications to correct or rephrase in the future.

Complexity and living systems

The focus of Cronin and his co-workers has been on biochemicals (Ladyman et al. 2013) but their ideas have been applied widely. They noted that living systems,

unlike inanimate matter, have the distinguishing ability to generate many copies of complex objects, such as molecules. We provide in part 3 several examples of hierarchical assembly pathways, such as:

amino acids → protein domains →
 proteins → protein complexes →
 macromolecular assemblies →
 subcellular structures → organelles →
 cells → tissues → organs → organ
 systems → eukaryote organism.

We concur that it is reasonable to attribute living systems as the source of identical complex molecules because many examples are known, such as proteins, DNA, and RNA. It is also reasonable because sophisticated technologies are found in living organisms responsible for autonomous metabolism, homeostasis, growth, adaptation to changes, self-repair, and reproduction, all performed reliably for millions of generations. One would not expect the underlying infrastructure to be simple.

We address next the key concept of complexity.

Chemical intuitions on molecular complexity

Cronin and his collaborators are interested in explaining how ever more complex molecules could have arisen on earth. Most chemists encounter early in their education the notion of molecular complexity. This is often phrased as the observation that some molecules are more *complicated* than others. Characterizing molecules as more or less complex is influenced by concepts like the difficulty of memorizing the structures or describing them to others. Several pairs of molecules are shown in Figure 1. Most chemists and chemistry students would agree that the first member (A) of each pair is 'less complicated' than the second option

(B). Several principles underlie when molecules seem more complex. They tend to be larger, display less symmetry, have a wider variety of bond types, have more kinds of atoms, and have more chiral centers.

Figure 1. Examples of simpler (A) vs. more complicated or complex molecules (B). The repetitive element in example 'f' is shown in a yellow frame.

The quantitative reality of simpler vs. more complex molecules can be demonstrated by how their structures are described using symbols. The two most commonly used conventions for describing and storing chemical structures in digital files are SMILES (Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry System; Weininger, 1988; Weininger, 1989) and InChI (IUPAC International Chemical Identifier; Heller (2015)). Both describe atoms and bonds, their connectivity, branching, cyclic structures, stereochemistry, isotopes, charges, and radicals. InChI formalism can also describe different tautomers. Examining the length and variety of symbols necessary to describe molecules in SMILES and InChI form reveals a strong correlation with what chemists intuitively associate with molecule complexity.

There is generally also a correlation between molecule complexity and how difficult it would be to devise a synthetic route, since all the kinds of bonds, each functional group, all branching, and each stereoisomer must be taken into account.

More formal concepts of molecular complexity

Considering the central role of complexity in AT, it is valuable to clarify its meaning. Complexity has been extensively explored by mathematicians and computer scientists, particularly in the context of symbol sequences representing objects or concepts. A key insight is that sequences with redundancy or predictability can be compressed into more concise representations. These compact sequences can often be used to reconstruct the original sequence, either exactly or to a sufficient degree of fidelity. As a simple example,

Run 2 miles, rest 1 min. Run 2 miles, rest 1 min. Run 2 miles, rest 1 min. (1)

could be re-expressed more compactly as:

Repeat 3 times: Run 2 miles, rest 1 min (2)

This is analogous to recognizing in Figure 1-f how the entire molecule on the left side could be expressed as “repeat the framed feature 5 times”.

In formal mathematical analyses of complexity, when two sequences of equal length are compared, the sequence that can be compressed more effectively exhibits greater redundancy and is considered less complex. Various mathematical metrics have been established to quantify the complexity of such sequences.

Shannon Information quantifies the complexity of a string of characters by

measuring the amount of uncertainty or surprise associated with obtaining the next character in the sequence, with more unpredictable strings having higher information content (Shannon, 1948).

Kolmogorov complexity expresses the complexity of an object, such as a string, by measuring the length of the shortest possible algorithm or description that can generate that object (Kolmogorov, 1963).

Logical Depth quantifies the complexity of a pattern by measuring the computational resources, particularly the time, required to generate it from its most concise description (Bennett, 1995).

Effective Complexity focuses on capturing and retaining only the meaningful, structured patterns in a system, while ignoring or filtering out the random or meaningless parts (Gell-Mann and Lloyd, 1996).

Computational Complexity measures the resources required to solve a problem or perform a computation as a function of the input size, focusing on worst-case or average-case scenarios (Stockmeyer, 1987).

Methods like these to estimate complexity agree on several principles. Sequences with much redundancy and repetitive sections require fewer resources to be processed; are more predictable; and can be expressed more compactly.

Hierarchical assembly process

Many compression algorithms were developed decades ago and are heavily used in computer science to store and transmit sequences more efficiently. They often rely on the concept of a dictionary of previously found substrings in a sequence that can be referred to instead of repeating the same

sequences. Examples include run-length encoding (RLE), Huffman, and Lempel-Ziv (LZ)-based schemes such as LZ78 or LZW.

Elements found in the dictionary can be combined, or *assembled*, into ever larger substrings in a hierarchical manner. The logic is discussed next for assembling in 1 to 3 dimensions.

One-dimensional assemblies

One dimensional compression is very common in computer science. Figure 2 illustrates how the sequence BANANA can be assembled from a dictionary of components. First, the basic elements {B, A, N} are identified and added to the dictionary. These are used to build the target sequence. Each distinct substring formed is also added to the dictionary for possible reuse. Therefore, sequences having multiple copies of a substring (like NA in BANANA) can be represented more compactly, especially when the substrings are very long and numerous (Marshall et al., 2017; fig. 2). This is essentially how the LZW algorithm works.

Figure 2. Illustration of a linear assembly pathway based on letters to form the sequence BANANA. Starting from the three basic elements {B, A, N}, four joining operations are needed to construct the target word BANANA.

Two-dimensional assemblies

Figure 3 illustrates how a two-dimensional structure composed of non-random parts can be hierarchically broken down into a construction pathway, using different strategies.

Figure 3. Illustration of two assembly pathways using two colored blocks as the basic elements that can be aligned in two dimensions to form the target object. All possible undesired outcomes have been neglected. Two solutions are shown that benefit by symmetry or redundancy A: Shortest assembly pathway. B: Alternative but longer assembly pathway. ('A' is based on Marshall et al., 2021; fig. 1.)

Assemblies to produce molecules

In AT, chemical bonds are figuratively joined by overlapping the atoms of pre-existing simpler molecules. Six examples are shown in Figure 4 to illustrate the concept. This proposal is fundamental to Molecular Assembly theory, but has faced criticism. It is critically reviewed in part 2 of this series.

Three-dimensional assemblies

Three-dimensional assemblies are difficult to show in two dimensions, but are the most important category for AT. Technical artifacts, organisms, biochemicals, and abiotic chemicals all require assembly in three dimensions. This is discussed in part 3 of this series, in which we point out that humans design and manufacture complex 3-dimensional artifacts with the aid of analytical tools such as Bills of Materials (BOMs) and Product Breakdown Structure (PBS).

Molecular assemblies were inspired by mass spectrometry

Figure 4. Example of how Assembly Theory joins bonds and combines previously generated structures. (Extracted from Marshall et al. 2021, Supplementary Information p. 11.)

Joining bonds as done by Cronin and Walker and their collaborators, as shown in Figure 4, was inspired by mass spectroscopy (MS). Upon ionization, the parent molecule breaks into a wide variety of fragments, from which an electron has been removed. (Only cations are measured by MS). Figure 5-A shows the key fragments that result from acetone (CH_3COCH_3).

Figure 5. Influence of mass spectroscopy on Assembly Theory. A: key fragments produced from acetone during mass spectroscopy. B: Illustration of how the parent molecule acetone can be deduced by superimposing atoms and joining bonds as done in Assembly Theory.

In MS, fragment ions originate from the dissociation of multiple copies of each molecular species, with detection favoring the most thermodynamically stable cationic fragments. However, structural rearrangements can occur prior to

subsequent fragmentation events, resulting in complex spectral patterns characterized by numerous signals when analyzing large, intricate molecules. Comprehensive interpretation of these fragment ion distributions enables elucidation of the parent molecular structure.

The two examples in Figure 5-B show how the reconstruction is done. In both examples, two fragments were identified that originated from different copies of the same molecule or fragment. Taken together, one can deduce what structure would lead to both fragments. Importantly, the two fragments did not arise from a single molecule, but different copies of a molecule. Consequently, the reconstruction logic does not imply that the two fragments could react chemically to form the parental structure, for many reasons. One reason is that the total number of carbons in the two fragments add up to more carbons than the reconstructed parent.

Sometimes two fragments could derive from the same parent, such as the second and third fragments shown in Figure 5-A from acetone. But once again, even though their parental structure can be reconstructed, this does not imply that both fragments could react chemically to synthesize acetone. MS fragmentation of

molecules is not the mirror image of their synthesis.

Alternative reconstruction pathways can be devised from the rich variety of fragments produced during MS from many identical molecules. Careful deduction will identify the minimum number of fragment assembly steps required to identify the parent molecule, even if no particular parent molecule underwent that particular fragmentation pattern. This intuition seems to be the basis for the key concept in AT of minimum number of assembly steps. The molecular assembly pathway (MA) diagrams used in AT chemical synthesis reconstructions do not represent fragments being combined. However, the AT operations allowed must satisfy chemical valence rules. Although the chemical

details for a feasible chemical step are not identified in MA, presumably real chemistry is involved in some manner.

Unstated rules incorporated into assembly algorithms

Many unstated rules need to be implemented for any of the one- to three-dimensional assembly algorithms. Some are documented in Table I based on the example in Figure 2, and these apply to all repetitive assembly processes that need to be executed reliably. These rules are also taken into account by the technologies used to implement software-based algorithms. For example, rules 6 and 7 in Table I refer to the need for proper interfaces between the parts being assembled. Computer programs assume this implicitly.

Table I. Many unstated rules are necessary for the algorithms used in Assembly Theory to work. This applies to the software algorithms and also to physical implementations.

No.	Unstated assumptions (rules)	Example based on Figure 2
1	The algorithm always knows the target object and how to decompose it into elementary elements.	The target is BANANA. In principle, the basic elements could have been defined in many ways, such as combinations of straight and curved lines at various angles and sizes. Here the algorithm was prepared to recognize letters, like {A, B, N}.
2	The transformational operations are defined in advance.	Suppose the potential targets often contained large mirror image regions, for example ABCDEF ABCDEF FEDCBA. Now an operation X = 'add the mirror image of the last substring added' could be included in the list of operations.
3	The algorithm knows where to start.	The algorithm specifies the left-most element is the starting point.
4	The algorithm knows how to proceed for each step.	The algorithm knows to proceed from left to right along the target object in 1-dimension and keeps track of how much has already been processed of the target. Here parallel processing is not allowed, e.g., BA and NA cannot be formed simultaneously.
5	The algorithm knows not to modify the target once reached.	Once NANA has been added to BA nothing is allowed to change the final BANANA.
6	The acceptable spatial placement of each element is specified.	For example, if B and A were a kilometer apart it would not be apparent to what sequence they belong. This implies it must be known where each element ends. For example, the string III would require less space than MMM. Also, full or partial superposition is not allowed, such as placing one NA on top of another.
7	The acceptable orientations of each element is specified.	Here the initial orientation is not allowed to change. For example, rotating N could lead to a Z.
8	The parts remain stable once in place.	Once B has been attached to A, they remain together. In general, some dedicated technology used by assembly processes must ensure this.

The physical interfaces of components must be specially designed to prevent incorrect assembly orientations and locations, for example for the blocks shown in Figure 2. This is one of many problems faced by the physical assembly of molecules shown in Figure 4. Physically, nothing forces the individual molecules to lock into place correctly based on the geometric shapes used. Another serious problem is rule 2. There is nothing in nature that is able to identify in advance all the transformational operations needed (i.e., by modifying countless environmental details to discover now possible 'operations') to discover a pathway for any target complex molecule.

AT, like other compression algorithms, can be used with symbols such as letters or simple geometric shapes. The problem arises when each individual symbol

becomes an abstract representation for multiple processing details and even unrelated physical processes, as occurs in MA for chemical reactions. The unstated physical activities necessary are not identified nor taken into consideration in a quantitative metric of complexity. Specifically, an individual symbol could represent multiple chemical activities each requiring special solvents, catalysts, temperature changes, a different pH, reagents, etc. This concern is elaborated on in Part 2.

Critically, AT like other measures of complexity, neglects the processing details required to assemble physical objects. Figure 6 illustrates this concept by showing how two identical basic elements (wheels) are combined with a third basic element (and axle) to produce an intermediate

assemblage in one conceptual step. Details like how the wheels get raised unto the table, how the axle is lowered, how all the elements get properly aligned and interlocked, where the intermediate assemblage is then stored safely, and so on, are not taken into account when counting assembly steps.

Figure 6. In Assembly Theory assembly, complexity is calculated using the minimum number of steps required to combined simpler elements into more complex ones without including the processing details.

Introduction to the molecular assembly index

In AT, Cronin, Walter and their co-workers defined complexity as the minimum number of joining operations to build an object starting with a minimal set of basic building blocks. Presumably this means chemical structural complexity. The sub-units generated can be combined with either basic building blocks or other sub-units to form the final object. For chemicals, AT researchers defined joining by using bonds, superimposing atoms from each member to be linked together (Marshall et al., 2021; p. 3). The methodology takes valence rules into account, but no other chemical considerations. This resembles superimposing edges in Figure 3 to align squares but with a critical difference. The

ends of chemical bonds are defined by atoms, and superimposing them is physically impossible: matter would need to disappear. (Physically, more than one atom would often occupy the same location according to the MA methodology).

Different algorithms have been developed to calculate the shortest pathway, called the assembly index, a_i , to assemble an object. (The a_i was formerly called Pathway Complexity, and for chemicals it is referred to as Molecular Assembly, MA). A ‘split-branch’ algorithm is usually used but often fails to identify the correct (i.e., shortest) a_i for large search spaces. However, it is faster than the other algorithms and provides a good approximation.

Assembling an object as done in AT is mathematically equivalent to finding a compressed representation by hierarchically building up subunits. More steps to form a compressed representation correlate with having more elements in the dictionary of components to select from. This implies greater complexity of the object. Consequently, a_i values would allow in principle the relative complexity of different objects to be ranked.

Assembly indices were developed to detect life

The assembly index was first developed as a detection system for life on earth and elsewhere (Marshall et al., 2021; p. 2):

Here we postulate that living systems can be distinguished from non-living systems as they produce complex molecules in abundance which cannot form randomly.

High abundance has not been defined, and in the AT literature is sometimes referred to as $>1,000,000$ copies and other times when sufficient to produce peaks in mass spectrometric analysis (Hazen et al., 2024).

The important claim is that from the assembly indices (Marshall et al., 2021; p. 2),

it is possible to unambiguously distinguish samples that contain molecules produced by life from those that do not.

Assembly indices allegedly correlate with real chemical processes

The original purpose of AT was to demarcate between chemicals of biotic vs abiotic origin. Its proponents state that their algorithms are not merely another method to quantify complexity. In a pioneering paper, they explained that

The motivation for the formulation of Pathway Complexity is to place a lower bound on the likelihood that a population of identical objects could have formed abiotically from an initial pool (Marshall et al., 2017; p. 3)

since they believe that (Marshall et al., 2017; p. 4),

The ability to reliably produce specific non-trivial trajectories through state space is, we propose, a characteristic unique to living systems.

In the case of prebiotic chemistry (Marshall et al., 2017; p. 4),

Pathway Complexity bounds the likelihood of natural occurrence by modelling a naive synthesis of the object from populations of its basic parts, where at any time pairs of existing objects can join in a single step.

Of course, assembly indices can only be ranked if the 'naive synthesis' correlates strongly with real chemical processes, a central point of this 3-part series.

We will discuss next how assembly indices are predicted empirically. Determining the

molecular assembly of an extra-terrestrial molecule, based on the minimum number of joining operations to construct it starting from its basic elements, requires that the molecular structure be known in advance. However, AT proponents argue that they can predict MA values directly from spectroscopic data. This is stated often in the AT literature and will be explained next.

Predicting Molecular Assembly (MA) from mass spectroscopy data

A surrogate for MA was obtained using mass spectroscopy (MS). Cronin and his co-workers reasonably expected that more complex molecules would generate spectra having more peaks than simpler molecules since generally, more complex molecules would be larger; have a wider range of bond types; and less symmetry.

Tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS) experiments were performed on 100 molecules, and the number of peaks generated for each was determined (Marshall et al., 2021). Then the MA value for each of the 100 molecules was calculated using a computer program by a "split-branch" algorithm. A linear regression equation was found with a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.89$ to predict MA values, but the equation found was not reported.

Using predicted MA to identify extra-terrestrial life

Cronin and his co-workers collected mixtures of four categories of materials, namely abiotic, biological, dead, and inorganics. The 15 most intense peaks were identified, representing the intact 15 molecules in highest concentration. Each of these was selectively isolated, individually fragmented (the MS2 process), and the number of peaks found was used with the regression equation to predict MA values for each molecule. This led to a distribution

of values for all the mixtures. They found that only mixtures from living or technology-created systems had some compounds with MA > 15 (Marshall et al., 2021). The authors concluded that their method could be used to send MS equipment to extraterrestrial locations to predict the highest MA values of molecules and potentially identify evidence of life.

However, the cutoff of a molecular assembly ≥ 15 for biosignatures has been challenged by the observation that some large terrestrial abiotic molecule-like heteropolyanions assemble in aqueous solution as precursors to some mineral crystals, and have molecular assembly indices as large as 21 (Hazen et al., 2024).

Correlation between MA and MS complexity is expected

Large compounds with less symmetry, more heteroatoms, complex branching, etc. will produce a wide range of MS fragments. Consequently, the number of MS peaks will correlate with the number of assembly steps required by algorithms to find the shortest MA. This is not surprising, since both obtain their values from an identical, static molecular structure. Since a vast number of identical parent molecules will be present in an MS sample, all or most fragments able to form will likely be found in the spectra.

However, correlation does not prove causation. The compression algorithms that reuse subparts to produce a target structure have no chemical correspondence, a matter elaborated on in part 2 of this series. AT assumes that an existing structural shape can be doubled and automatically combined, as shown in the example in Figure 7-A (Jirasek et al. 2024, fig. 1). The line in red shows where the algorithm overlaps two bonds, which implies physically that a chemical bond must form

between two C=C groups. The atoms at the position boxed in yellow must overlap.

Unfortunately, chemistry involves more than positioning shapes and expecting them to ‘lock together’. A series of chemical reactions would be necessary to bind the two molecules shown, each requiring a distinctive solvent, temperature, pH, etc. In Figure 7-B a chemical synthesis strategy is shown, based on placing a suitable functional group ‘Y’ at the necessary position. An alternative approach might be to convert the molecules into free radicals as shown in Figure 7-C. However, random processes to create free radicals would lead to an incomprehensible mixture of virtually everything except the bimolecular reaction intended.

Figure 7. Redrawn from part of Jirasek et al. 2024, fig. 1. A: The single assembly step as foreseen by Assembly Theory. B: Representing the single step with a plausible chemical structure. The Y group could be H, OH, a halide, etc. C: Assembly Theory example of joining cyclohexane rings from Sharma et al., 2023, fig. 1-C. The colored rectangles represent the position atoms would need to overlap.

Figure 7-C provides a simpler example of why the kinds of bond joins used in AT do

not match nor correlate with chemical realities. Mixing two molecules of cyclohexane (12 carbons in total) won't lead to a 10-carbon fused ring decalin, nor would mixing decalin with cyclohexane produce a 3-ring fused molecule (Figure 7-C). This is analogous with what was shown in Figure 3, in which squares were aligned together with several unstated rules documented in Table I. There are no such unstated chemical rules being applied by nature. Suitable physical interfaces are necessary for the correct chemical reactions to occur so that the parts can 'lock everything in place' correctly, and these interfaces need to be part of the pathway design. Typically, multiple chemical reactions would need to be designed to implement the assembly indicated by superimposing the geometric shapes.

Predicting Molecular Assembly from infrared data

Cronin's group also predicted the number of infrared (IR) spectroscopy peaks a series of 10,000 molecules would produce in the fingerprint region (400–1500 cm^{-1}). They used the xTB software that is based on a semiempirical model (Bannwarth et al., 2021). The Molecular Assemblies were also calculated approximately using a fast algorithm ('split-branch' assembly index) that incorporates concurrency, written in the Go programming language (Jirasek et al., 2024). This led to the regression equation

$$\text{MA} = 0.21 \times n \text{ peaks} - 0.15 \quad (r = 0.86) \quad (3)$$

A correlation between MA and IR is not surprising, since both obtain their values from an identical, static molecular structure. More complex molecules will tend to generate a larger number of IR peaks and will also require more elements in their

dictionary to generate a compressed representation of the structure.

Predicting Molecular Assembly from NMR data

In another study (Jirasek et al., 2024) the ^{13}C NMR spectra of the same 10,000 molecules used in the IR study were predicted with the tool NMRShiftDB (Kuhn and Schlörer, 2015). Different kinds of carbon nuclei, based on the number of attached hydrogens, were treated as separate variables. This led to the regression equation

$$\text{MA} = 1.3 \times \text{C} + 0.8 \times \text{CH} + 0.6 \times \text{CH}_2 + 0.3 \times \text{CH}_3 + 2.1 \quad (4)$$

with a correlation of $r = 0.87$, where C = quaternary, CH = tertiary, CH_2 = secondary, and CH_3 = primary carbons.

Once again, a good correlation is expected, as mentioned for the MS and IR studies, since the MA and ^{13}C NMR spectra are derived from the same static structure.

AT proponents often claim that assembly indices are *empirical numbers* and that AT is *experimentally testable*. For example (Caspermeyer, 2023),

A key feature of the theory is that it is experimentally testable (Caspermeyer, 2023).

Being able to test a theory experimentally adds substantially to its credibility. The basis for alleging testability is that correlation equations can be used to predict MA values, as explained in the following quote.

For molecules, computing the assembly index is not explicitly necessary, because the assembly index can be probed directly experimentally with high accuracy with spectroscopy techniques including mass spectroscopy, infrared,

and nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 327).

While spectroscopic data can certainly provide measures of molecular complexity, nothing measured in a laboratory quantifies nor explains what was necessary to actually manufacture those molecules. In other words, the predicted MA values are not actual measures of the minimal number of physical chemical steps needed assemble the target molecules. Therefore, AT is not a theory that explains the *origin of life* in any kind of testable manner. We agree with what all chemists would say, namely that more complex molecules tend to produce more complex MS, IR, and ¹³C spectra. However, a calculated MA complexity index would convey very little about the actual number of processing details necessary to synthesize molecules.

Predicting Molecular Assembly from molecular weight

As discussed above, chemists agree that generally larger molecules are more complex. Unsurprisingly, a strong correlation between the MA and MW has also been reported (Jirasek et al., 2024):

$$MA = 0.047 \times MW - 0.4 \quad (5)$$

substrings are reused using a pointer to their location, as done with the LZ77 algorithm.

using the same split-branch algorithm to estimate MA values used in the spectroscopic studies. (Only molecules with MW <500 g/mol were used in the model.) The authors noted correctly that most terrestrial molecules having MW >300 Da that are not simple oligomers or composed of heavy atoms, and not synthesized by humans, were manufactured by living organisms.

The Pearson Correlation coefficient, *r*, for eqn. (5) was not reported. This is unfortunate since finding the MW of a molecule is considerably easier than collecting and analyzing spectroscopic data. Perhaps the extra effort involved in spectroscopic analysis is not justified. The correlation eqn. (5) would be expected to be especially good for nonsymmetric organic molecules lacking repeating units and heavy elements.

Using AT to compress gene sequences

Instead of using chemical bonds as done for molecules, AT has also been used with nucleobases as elementary building blocks to construct compressed representations of gene sequences. An example is shown in Figure 8 in which previously used

Figure 8. Assembly tree of a hypothetical gene sequence X using the four nucleobases {A, C, G, T} as the elementary basic elements. The original 60-letter sequence X was compressed into a 36-letter sequence Y . Traced with slight modification from Liu et al., 2021; p. 5.

Compression of long DNA or RNA sequences to save storage space or transmission effort is useful, but AT does not claim to have developed a better compression algorithm than other already available. AT's goal is to make contributions to evolutionary theory and the origin of life, as discussed in Part 2 and 3 of this series. The algorithm used in Figure 8 is indeed a measure of structural complexity, but the algorithm does not mimic how RNA and DNA sequences thousands of nucleotides long formed, either in cells or abiotically. A measure of structural complexity need not be a relevant or adequate measure of physical assembly complexity.

AT recognizes that a vast number of chemical reactions would have existed abiotically, with almost none having value for life. The challenge is to find causal factors, or *selection*, that favored the 'right' pathways but without any foreknowledge or goals. The actual synthetic routes used are stated to be perhaps unknowable, so instead, assembly algorithms are proposed based on aligning shapes that represent chemicals. These are called assembly

pathways. Although the aligning operations cannot be mapped to actual chemical processes, AT proposes that the shortest assembly pathway communicates a lower bound for the amount of selectivity required by the true physical routes taken.

DISCUSSION

Specific portions of molecules have properties that can be sensed by spectroscopic methods such as MS, IR, and NMR. More complex molecules possess more microenvironments that can influence the spectroscopic outcomes, leading to a greater variety of signals.

Aspects of molecules that chemists associate with complexity, like a wide variety of bond types, were mentioned above. Molecules with more copies of identical features are also considered more complex. For example, a molecule consisting of a single benzene ring seems less complex than 99 such rings fused linearly. In a video presentation, Cronin offered a definition of an Assembly Index that reflects this intuition,

(<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Yru4Nz27saQ>) where he recommended to

basically, look at the stuff, count the number of objects that are identical, and then for each object class, cut them up and you get the Assembly Index.

AT became controversial when its supporters claimed that the numerical values resulting from their algorithms were quantitative indicators of how molecules were or could be actually manufactured. Note that the phrase *assembly index* is used instead of *complexity index*.

Mass spectroscopy fragmentation is not the reverse of bond formation

The origins of AT are closely linked to mass spectroscopy (MS). It is important to understand that the fragmentation process resulting from MS is not an indicator of how a molecule was synthesized. Two MS fragment cations would not have reacted chemically together. In theory, adding an electron to both cations would lead to free radicals that might bond together but the conditions that form free radicals would 'wreak havoc' on all the organic material in that environment. The radicals formed would be so unstable they would quickly react with anything able to restore the valence rules.

Leading proponents of AT claim that (Slocombe and Walker, 2024; p. 949),

MA is the only molecular complexity measure that is measurable, whereas other molecular complexity measures, including topological, substructure, and graph-theoretic approaches, require prior structural elucidation.

In what sense are MA values measurable without requiring prior structural elucidation? In the AT literature, MA values are calculated using algorithms that require knowing the target structure. The above

quote seems to allude to the use of correlation equations that don't *measure* but estimate MA values. However, obtaining these equations always required a prior structural elucidation of sample data used to find the equations. For every molecule in the sample data, an MA value and some criteria from the MS spectrum are used (different parts of the MS data were selected for different empirical correlations). MA values and MS spectra both correlate strongly with the complexity of a molecule and thus they must also correlate with each other.

IR and NMR spectra also correlate strongly with molecular complexity. In a recent publication, it was stated that (Slocombe and Walker, 2024; p. 951),

Both IR and NMR will agnostically indicate the complexity of a molecule defined by MA since assembly theory states that MA utilizes unique irreducible motifs to construct the molecule.

However, MA, IR, and NMR will correlate with any reasonable definition of molecular structural complexity. The regression equations used sample data based on prior structural elucidations to calibrate an empirical relationship between two sets of values, such as number of IR peaks and MA values.

The correlation equations between spectral data and MA won't be perfect for several reasons. One is that there can also be physical influences between structural motifs. For example, these interactions can affect how IR and NMR absorb electromagnetic radiation and therefore display additional peaks that are not captured by MA algorithms.

Analogous correlations could be found for other measures of complexity besides MA, such as the total number of elements found

in the dictionary to construct a compressed representation of each molecule. One could then also claim this criterion for complexity 'is measurable'. Clearly, regression equations could be developed from spectral data to predict any reasonable measure of structural complexity, this is not a distinctive feature of only MA.

Why do Molecular Assemblies need to be calculated?

AT is based on the observation that molecules associated with life are often far more complex than abiotic molecules, and are generated in large copy numbers. Since the early AT papers focus on distinguishing abiotic from biotic molecules, it is not apparent why MA values need to be calculated and used to demarcate biotic from non-biotic molecules. MS criteria such as the number of peaks could be used directly to classify the test molecules as biotic or abiotic using methods like logistic regression. This well-known statistical method offers an important advantage of giving a probability measure that the classification is correct.

Many other statistical techniques can also be tested using whichever combination of features from the MS spectra empirically give the best results. For example, QSAR (Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship) methodologies allow the inclusion of arbitrary structural parameters to find the best empirical models.

Using the MA methodology introduces unnecessary errors. The MA values for molecules of unknown structure must be predicted from MS peaks using a correlation equation (Marshall et al., 2021). The $r = 0.89$ reported corresponds to $r^2 = 0.79$, so 21% of the variability of the MA values cannot be accounted for. Furthermore, the MA values used to develop the equation were only estimates of

the true MA values, calculated from an algorithm.

It is surprising, that the results from long-established and intuitively straightforward classification methods lacking unnecessary errors were not reported in the AT publications. Considerable effort was expended, even though no extraterrestrial molecules of biotic origin are available to validate the major assumptions.

A Disassembly Index from MS spectra

Benner, a chemist, also opines that inventing an assembly index serves no purpose. He wrote that (Benner, 2023),

We could simply define a disassembly number that is equal to the number of different fragments found for a single molecule in MS2. This would avoid confusing big molecules that have repetitive, low information, structures from those that have non-repetitive, high information structures.

This disassembly number could be used to classify different categories of molecules, such as biotic vs. abiotic.

CONCLUDING COMMENTS

Here in Part 1, we have focused on the historical background of AT, and suggest that researchers can see if it offers benefits for the stated purpose, namely, to classify molecules into different categories. At this point in our analysis, MA does not seem very controversial. Lately, however, a variety of dramatic claims were spread in social media and professional publications, in particular, that AT explains and quantifies evolutionary theory. We will address these contentious issues in Parts 2 and 3 of this series.

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